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INGAME
Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation

INGAME

INGAME – Gaming for Social Inclusion and Civic Participation – A holistic approach for a cultural shift in education and policy

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WP4/4.4. INGAME Training and Policy Resource Manual

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1. Introduction

Aim/Objectives of Document

The aim of this document is to present a common approach for the implementation of Work Package 5 (WP5) of the INGAME project. Its specific objectives are the following:

- To interpret and explain the conditions and requirements of WP5, according to the project proposal.
- To elaborate on who the WP5 target groups are, and how they can be approached.
- To set a shared timeline for the implementation of WP5.
- To analyse the contents of output 5.1. (Training Material)

2. Work Package 5 – Conditions and Requirements

The purpose of Work Package 5 is to facilitate the capacity building of professionals in the field of youth work and training through structured online courses and face-to-face local Workshops with experts. The capacity-building effort focuses on providing methods and material that will assist target groups to integrate game-based learning in their professional practices. WP5 is divided in the following 5 activities/tasks:

5.1. Creation of training material [Lead: CSI, Part.: All partners]

The Training Material will be in line with output 3.2. *INGAME Curriculum and Content*. The content generated in 5.1. will explain effective methodologies, teaching techniques, tools, and activities to integrate game-based learning in pedagogical practices. The material will also focus on how to utilize

the INGAME project and, specifically, the game developed as part of the project. Finally, the material should have a total duration of **25 hours of learning** in blended format (F2F and Online)

5.2. Selection of the participating youth centres/CSOs/HEI organisations (Lead: CSI, Part.: All partners)

Each partner will establish contacts and signed agreement of collaboration (see Annex 1) in the framework of the project with several multipliers and stakeholders. The selected organisations will participate in the pilot actions and their staff will be trained through the material developed in 5.1.

5.3. Training of youth workers, educators, decision makers, youth leaders, policy makers, academics, stakeholders (Lead: CSI, Part.: All partners)

The objective of 5.3 is to provide trainings in blended format (synchronous/asynchronous, f-t-f/online). The training will be provided to more than **100 persons per partner** (at least 900 persons to be trained in total). Activity 5.3. has two phases:

- Online Course: a short course teaching practical aspects required for the implementation of the project and useful teaching and pedagogical methods that reflect game-based learning practices. The online course will be available as an open educational resource on the project website and will facilitate asynchronous training.
- Local Workshops at schools (online or face-to-face): in combination with the online course, the training will be completed through two-day workshops (3 hours each) at the local level.

5.4. Implementation of pilot actions

The game developed will be implemented in partner countries, among at least 100 youth per country for 3 months and minimum 10 hours of game play per person (at least 900 youth in total).

5.5. Final Evaluation and conclusions

The project partners and the participants in both educators' implementation and youth pilot testing will evaluate the actions.

3. Target Groups and Stakeholders

The direct target groups of the project are **EU youth** (16-35 years old) and the expected impact on this target group is to maximize their awareness, understanding and knowledge and shift their culture of action on social inclusion, gender equality, social justice, and civic participation.

Moreover, secondary target groups are the **youth trainers** and **youth workers** dealing with youth. This includes professionals in the field of formal education (e.g., secondary education and higher education), and also informal and non-formal education. The expected impact on this target group is to improve their professional skills in social inclusion education through innovative digital environments, like games, structures training and pilot actions by which these professionals will practice new methodologies and teaching techniques aimed at shifting youth culture towards inclusiveness, justice, and participation. Emphasis may be given on marginalized or groups which are socially excluded.

Finally, each partner will need to acquire **10 collaboration agreements** with local stakeholders or target group representatives by completing the following tasks:

1. Identify specific target groups or stakeholders at the local level, by using Table 1 below as a guiding tool.
2. Invite the identified stakeholders/target groups to sign a collaboration agreement to support the activities of the INGAME project. A template of the collaboration agreement is provided in Annex 1 (in English).

Type of Target Groups	Contacts (Name of organisation/individuals)	Contact Info (e.g., email, phone, social media)
Primary and Secondary Schools		
Public authorities		
Teachers and teachers associations		
Gaming community Members		
NGOs (especially organisations promoting social inclusion)		
Migrant pupils and their families		
Type of Stakeholders	Contacts (Name of organisation/individuals)	Contact Info (e.g., email, phone, social media)
Youth training institutions		
Higher Education Institutions		
Research and Development Centres		
Public Institutions and Social Services		
Local Community Groups and Youth Organisations		

Civil Society Organisations		
Professional Networks (especially in education)		
Policy Makers/ Public Authorities		

Table 1: *INGAME Target Groups and Stakeholders*

4. Timeline and Structure of WP5 Activities

Table 2 below presents an analytical list of WP5 activities, with corresponding suggested deadlines for each:

Activity	Tasks	Deadline
Activity 5.1.	Training Material Draft	01.10.2021
	Feedback from Partners	01.06.2021
	Training Material Final (English)	01.08.2022
	Training Material Translations	15.09.2022
Activity 5.2.	Collection of Collaboration Agreements	01.07.2022
	Face-to-Face/Online Workshops	15.09.2022 – 15.11.2022
Activity 5.3.	INGAME Pilot Implementation	15.09.2022 – 15.12.2022

Table 2: *WP5 Activities, Tasks and Deadlines*

Structure of WP5 Activities

The structure of WP5 is divided to three phases:

1. Content development – Training Material (Activity 5.1.)
2. Training of Educators (Activity 5.2.)
3. Piloting of game with youth/students (Activity 5.3.)

4.1. Training Material

The main purpose of the training manual is to build the capacity of educators (including youth mentors/workers) to incorporate game-based learning in their professional practice. As such, the manual should contain the following key components (with sub-components included):

- State-of-the-art pedagogical approaches to gamified/game-based learning
 - Assessment Activities
- Lesson plans and practical approaches
 - Assessment Activities

- WP3 3.2 INGAME Curriculum and Content
 - Integrate as a whole
 - Include analysis of material in thematic units
 - Assessment Activities
- INGAME Game
 - Playing Instructions
 - Game Testing
 - Assessment Activities

In addition, the Training Manual will cover the following themes, based on the work done in WP3:

THEME A: **Towards Active Citizenship**

THEME B: **Reclaiming Gender Equality**

THEME C: **Reinforcing Social Inclusion**

THEME D: **The INGAME Experience**

Finally, the Training Manual will incorporate gamified components (e.g., badges, medals) in the evaluation of learners, as well as multimedia material in the presentation of its content.

4.2. Training of Educators

This phase involves face to face (or online) workshops in each partner country. The workshops will be delivered to 100 professionals in the field of youth and education and will be based on the training course (training material) developed in Activity 5.1.

The total duration of the course will be 25 hours. The duration of learning will be covered by a) **two synchronous workshops** with the target groups, and b) the availability of further **asynchronous learning** through the training material developed in A.5.1.

The suggested time for the synchronous learning is **3 hours for each workshop, with the rest of the time covered by asynchronous learning online. The evaluation of progress and learning outcomes achieved will be conducted through assessment activities which will be integrated in the training material. After the completion of the online course, participants will receive a certificate of participation.*

4.3. Piloting of Game

The implementation of piloting actions will take place between September-November 2022. The piloting will follow the launch event for the game in Cyprus (September 2022). Each partner will need to cover 100 participants (local youth/students). The participants will need to spend 10 hours piloting the game. This duration of time will contain the actual gameplay and evaluation assessment exercises following the completion of the game. Access to participants should be pursued both through dissemination and communication actions, as well as through the local stakeholders and target group representatives who signed collaborative agreements with partners to support the INGAME project.

4.4. Guidelines to play the game

To access the game, go to the website: <https://ingame.erasmus.site/>, and then select GAME from the menu at the top (<https://ingame.erasmus.site/engame/>).

Registration is then required. Once all fields have been filled in and consent to the privacy policy has been ticked, the user is redirected directly to the game. If the user has previously logged in to the game, simply select the 'I am already registered, take me to the game' option below.

ENGAME

Registration form for the pilots

Name

Surname

Email

Country of residence

Country of origin

Year of birth

Gender

woman

man

non-binary

prefer not to answer

Profession/Occupation

student

internship

employed

self-employed

unemployed

I Agree to **Privacy Policy**

I Agree to **Privacy Policy**

SUBMIT I am already registered, take me to the game.

Source of images: <https://ingame.erasmus.site/pl/engame/>

The game's start screen then appears. The user selects one of the 8 available languages.

The ENGAME game consists of levels that address the following topics:

- GENDER
- EDUCATION
- SOCIAL INCLUSION
- CITY LIFE
- ENVIRONMENT

- CIVIC ENGAGEMENT AND CIVIC PARTICIPATION

In the bottom right-hand corner of the start screen, there is a button that launches a tutorial on how to play the game.

After clicking on the icon, the player will be introduced to the basic rules of the game.

Movement of the character in the game is via the keyboard. The arrow keys allow the character to move right, left and up.

During each level of the game, the player must collect several items. This is necessary to progress to the next level. Collecting them is done with the mouse.

The number of items the player needs to collect can be found in the box at the top left of the game screen.

The player can move to the next room (scene) by clicking the mouse on the door when its colour is green.

There is an element in the game called Mentor. It appears at various points in the game and provides the player with valuable information and questions for reflection.

In order for the player to move on to the next level (on a different topic), he or she must pass a test consisting of a number of questions that relate to the content covered while progressing through a particular level of the game.

To move to the next level,
you must pass the test!

The game gives the player the opportunity to absorb content on socially relevant topics and learn through play. All 6 levels are an excellent opportunity to gain awareness of the 6 areas, which are presented in an accessible way for the participants of the game.

Enjoy playing and learning!

INGAME Team

Source of images: <https://ingame.erasmus.site/wpcontent/themes/InGametheme2/game/index.html>

ANNEX 1

Collaborative agreement template.

Collaborative Agreement for INGAME project

This agreement is to confirm that the [**Institution Name**], represented by [**Signatory Name**] in the position of [**Position of Signatory**], hereby declares to be willing to support the activities of the project INGAME, funded by the European Commission, aiming at raising awareness of young people and the general public regarding civic participation and social inclusion. In developing a game-based learning approach to be implemented across Europe, the INGAME project will promote high quality education for youth.

The main objectives of INGAME are:

- Enhancing the acquisition of social and civic competences, fostering knowledge, understanding and ownership of values and fundamental rights.
- INGAME will enhance the overall knowledge of educators, providing them with an updated state-of-art, best practices and roadmap that will guide further action towards more inclusive educative environments.
- INGAME will encourage and support the adoption of innovative solutions/ approaches/ practices (co-developed, tested and assessed) by the key actors, including local communities and authorities and other relevant stakeholders.

This document represents a statement for the support of the project and the implementation activities planned under its schedule. This document does not establish any type of formal contract and will not imply any kind of financial input.

Month ##, 2022

Signature

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